

THE IMPORTANCE OF KNOWING THE BASIC PRINCIPLES OF HEAT TREATMENT OF FOOD IN A MODERN WAY

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Abstract: *In recent years, culinary experts have been actively searching hand in hand for methods of heat treatment, preparation of meat, which will contribute to increasing the quality of taste but also reducing the negative consequences for human health. Starting from the assumption that taste is the basic starting point and that we have to meet modern medical requirements I will provide a balance of mutual satisfaction in this paper. The paper shows the results how much we know and apply the principles of food processing and preparation in the area of the coastal zone of Montenegro. Scientific facts will work in favor of culinary requirements.*

INTRODUCTION

The proper nutrition of people today is given increasing importance not only in the most economically developed countries of the world, but also in all others. More and more, food and nutrition are associated with the preservation of health and even with the treatment of certain diseases. Recommendations on proper nutrition of certain categories of the population are made by nutritionists based on the results of numerous scientific researches. At the same time, the choice of foods and the method of their preparation must be such that they satisfy the energy and nutritional needs of a person, but also have desirable gastronomic properties such as an attractive appearance, smell and taste. With the economic development of society, the customs of food preparation and consumption are also changing more and more. People prepare food not only in their homes, but very often consume it in restaurants and other catering establishments. When preparing food at home and in the catering industry, apart from fresh raw materials, various industrial semi-finished and ready meals are used more and more. As their preparation is simple and fast, the food industry is increasingly expanding the range and increasing the production of such products.

The research that was carried out for the purposes of this work aims to present the importance of knowing food processing in the way it is done today, as well as the analysis of the safety aspect that accompanies food preparation technology. In addition, the knowledge of employees who prepare food and handle food in the further process of service will be presented, as well as the very genesis of the acquisition of knowledge that employees have at their disposal. The research was conducted at the beginning of the preparation of the tourist season in the Republic of Montenegro, in the cities of Budva, Tivat, Herceg Novi and Podgorica in 4-star hotels and restaurants that are considered high-category and quality restaurants. The time interval of the conducted research is from May 1 to 20, 2022. The questionnaire was adapted to the circumstances and organization of work in gastronomy in the mentioned area, and the questionnaire by the author De Boeck, Jacxsens with with associates¹².

¹² De Boeck, E., Mortier, V., Jacxsens, L., Vlerick, P. (2017) Towards an extended food safety culture model: Studying the moderating role of burnout and job stress, the mediating role of food safety knowledge and motivation in the relation between food safety climate and food safety behavior, DOI: [10.1016/j.tifs.2017.01.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2017.01.004)

The questionnaire provides answers to basic questions such as:

- a) Assessment of basic knowledge about the importance of the safety aspect of food preparation
- b) Methods of food preparation in facilities that are not standardized and certified

The 8-question questionnaire gives answers in four parts:

- a) Age and gender characteristics of the respondents
- b) Work experience
- c) Educational structure
- d) Certification and degree of risk

Answers were collected in such a way that questionnaires were sent via e-mail, which were answered by managers of catering establishments in consultation with kitchen chefs. Out of 60 sent questionnaires, 52 respondents provided complete answers, which is a sufficient sample for research of this kind.

Today's aspirations of people when it comes to nutrition are for food to retain as much of its natural state as possible, and to adapt it to today's habits and provide a sense of enjoyment when consuming it, but to ensure that the safety aspect is not violated and to eliminate potential consequences for the health of the guests, but also employees. Therefore, this paper also aims to give a brief overview of the latest achievements regarding the influence of technological parameters during heat treatment in the foreground of the temperature in the center of the sample and different heat treatment procedures (cooking and baking) on changes in proteins, meat color, meat rheological properties, pH of meat, water binding capacity, chemical properties and sensory properties of meat.

Finally, we find the important and special significance of this work in the summative review of traditional thermal processing methods that evolve according to scientific achievements. In other words, from the culinary aspect, we adapt traditional methods to medical-scientific requirements.

HEAT TREATMENT METHODS

In cooking, heat treatment is accepted and considered as the basic treatment of foodstuffs for human consumption. Based on heat transfer, four heat treatment procedures are distinguished, namely:

- a) heat treatment in a dry environment;
- b) heat treatment in a humid environment;
- c) thermal bream in a combined environment;

d) heat treatment with microwaves;

Heat treatment in a dry environment

Heat processing in a dry environment is done using air or fat, which makes meat processed by this method richer in taste. This method includes: gratin, roasting, baking in the oven, grilling, sauteing, frying in shallow fat and frying in deep fat.

Gratination

So, fry the dish from above until an even color is formed on the surface of the dish. The temperature during the process is from 250°C to 300°C. There are three methods of gratin. The first is the "complete way", and the process takes place in such a way that the raw food is placed in a dish whose bottom is greased with butter and already covered with a thin layer of gratin sauce, and the rest of the sauce is poured over the food from above and baked. The second is the "quick way" and the process is the same as with the "full" way, and the difference is that the food is pre-prepared, i.e. previously exposed to some technological procedure. Then the third way is the "easy way" and it is most often used with pasta, and that is by pouring the raw or cooked pasta with the gratin sauce and putting it to gratin. Dishes that are prepared in this way are gratinized at a lower temperature so that the sauce is easily combined with the food.

Roasting

Roasting is the oldest way of preparing meat, as well as other foods, and to this day, food from a spit or grill, from a pan or oven, with or without a lid, with the obligatory addition of fat, is still a favorite in all parts of the world. When frying, the food is immersed in oil at a temperature of 180°C to 200°C. Nutritionists warn that food prepared by baking and frying is harmful to health, but, unfortunately, most people are still not ready to give up such a snack. The grill should be well heated so that the surface of the meat is browned quickly and the nutritious and aromatic juices do not leak out. Pieces of meat that are grilled in the form of a steak should be flat. All bumps and bulges will burn faster, so you won't be able to bake the piece nicely and evenly. Hard pieces of meat should be softened in a pan before baking. In addition, the pan in which the meat is placed is seasoned, so the steak absorbs a fine aroma. The meat should be pounded and coated with oil, which is also used to coat the grate. White and light meat must be cooked at an even temperature. In order for the meat to be juicy, it should be coated with liquid fat (oil or melted fat) during baking. Dark meats, which are juicy by nature, should be roasted first on the highest heat, and then continue roasting on normal heat. Fry the breaded small pieces on a moderate heat

coated with a little oil or butter until they turn golden yellow. Meat for grilling is not salted, because salt draws the juice out of it and the meat remains dry. Exceptions are skewers and chicken. You can also grill vegetables, especially hard ones such as tomatoes, celery, and mushrooms. It is coated with oil, and the tomato should be cut from the top in the shape of a cross. Very juicy vegetables should be baked wrapped in aluminum foil. Potatoes that are fried a little on the grill after cooking are very tasty. Cooked, peeled and cooled potatoes should be cut lengthwise, put a thick piece of melted cheese between the halves, coat the potatoes with oil, sprinkle with red pepper and pepper, wrap in foil and grill on the side of the grill for about 20 minutes. Grilling in foil has many advantages. The meat is softer, juicier and retains a stronger and better taste. The main procedure is as follows: the foil is coated with oil, the thing to be baked is placed and everything is tightly wrapped so that the juice does not leak out. In his book *Catering*, Professor Bobić says that mixed content can also be baked (Bobić, 1994):

- a) fish mixed with onion rings
- b) liver with diced celery and a few spinach leaves.

When serving, the foil is simply loosened and the dish is brought to the table in it. Fish can be sprinkled with flour before grilling. Then their crust is crispier. They should be coated with oil and not turned until one side is browned. Baking in the oven is a method similar to the previous one with also suitable temperatures from 175°C to 220°C.

Sauteing

Sauteing means to fry food briefly and quickly in hot, shallow fat in an open pan. Take it out of the pan and put butter in it, add stock, wine or some sauce, spices and let it boil, then return the sauteed food to the pan to soften in the sauce and take on quality properties. The temperature should range from 160°C to 240°C. The heat carrier is fat. The container and the fat should be hot so that the protein in the meat quickly coagulates and forms an outer layer that protects and seals the food.

Frying

Simple dishes can be prepared by frying: meat, fish and vegetables, etc. However, other dishes can also be fried, such as usually various pastas or meat additions. Oil, grease and butter can be used for frying, which is called *friture*. Butter is the least suitable for this purpose, because it does not reach a sufficient temperature. When butter is very hot, it is 132°C, very hot fat is 200°C, and very hot oil is 300°C. Butter is not used for frying because it contains a lot of water, while lard can be used for larger pieces, and oil for small pieces, which require the highest temperature. The oil tolerates heat best, so it can be used for the longest time. There are usually two types of fryers, one, which has already been used for frying, can be used for frying

fish, and the other is fresh, which is used for all other dishes. In order for fryers to be used as long as possible, care should be taken that they are never heated too much, otherwise they will turn black and cannot be used again. For frying, we need very hot fat or oil, and this is known by the fact that weak steam rises from the fat or oil. The fryer is hot if the slice of raw potato sizzles a little. There is a well-known trick of the old culinary masters to check the temperature of fat. "You can also put a little dough in the fat, so if it immediately rises to the surface, it is a sign that the fat is good for frying." Food is usually coated in flour, egg and breadcrumbs before frying, so it is professionally called breading. Breaded foods, various types of pasta, and foods dipped in liquid dough can be fried. Some dishes are fried uncovered, and some need to be covered in the beginning, and then fried uncovered. When frying, it is important that the food is completely dry and that enough fat or oil is used to maintain the necessary heat for frying. It must also be taken into account that foods reduce the temperature of the fat, so it is necessary that the initial temperature of the fat is always higher. In addition, you should try not to let the temperature of the fat drop during frying. Therefore, you should fry quickly and in hot fat, because otherwise the food "drinks" the fat and cannot be tasty, nor good for eating. As Professor Drašković points out in the book *Gastronomy* (Drašković, 2006).

Heat treatment in a humid environment

Heat treatment in a wet environment includes:

- a) cooking,
- b) ponding,
- c) simmering,
- d) mating.

Cooking

Cooking food means that food is kept in water with a temperature of up to 100°C, while during blanching, mostly vegetables, they are briefly immersed in water that is at the boiling point. *Blanching*, along with steaming, is also the healthiest way to prepare food, because this way nutrients are best preserved. Cooking in its own juice involves heat treatment during which neither water nor any other liquid is added, but the food is cooked in the water released from it at a temperature of over 100 °C.

Baring

Poaching is a method of heat processing in a moist environment that uses convection to transfer heat from a liquid to a food. During soaking, the food is immersed in a liquid that is heated to a temperature between 71°C and 82°C, which shows only slight movement but no bubbles.

Poaching

Method for preparing eggs, fish, etc. when food is exposed to quick and short heat treatment in hot water or wine, milk, oil. eg: A fresh egg is broken and thrown directly into boiling water, in which it is boiled for two minutes, and from which it is removed with a French spoon.

Heat treatment in a combined environment

Heat treatment in a combined environment refers to heat treatment using dry and wet heat treatment, we distinguish between:

- a) stuffing,
- b) poeling.

Stewing is similar to the 'slow' cooking technique, with the difference that incomparably less liquid is used during stewing. Stewing is the best culinary method to soften tough pieces of meat or fibrous foods. By poeling, we tenderize tender meats in a covered container without water at a temperature of 140°C to 180°C. The heat carrier is hot moist air and fat. Fry vegetables such as red onions, celery and carrots in a pan with a little fat. Place beef or chicken on the vegetables.

INFLUENCE OF TEMPERATURE HEIGHT ON THE CHANGE OF TECHNOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF MEAT

The basic issue faced by culinary people all over the world today is changing the technological properties of food while maintaining the quality and taste structure. The process of the necessity of thermal processing of meat can be viewed from a medical-culinary aspect. Almost all meat products are heat-treated in some way in order to achieve the desired sensory and nutritional properties, as well as to meet the criteria regarding microbiological stability and product safety. The most common are two types of heat treatment in industrial conditions:

- a) heat treatment by cooking at atmospheric pressure or vacuum
- b) dry heat treatment by baking.

Many processes use autoclaves for cooking under increased pressure or steam cooking devices under atmospheric pressure (water baths). Products in these devices are generally immersed in hot water or heat treated with steam above the liquid phase. The rate of heat transfer depends on the heat treatment regime applied. In order to achieve the desired temperature of the product during the heat treatment, the device in which the heat treatment is carried out must provide a higher temperature than the one in the product. According to the authors (Boles and Swan, 1996), the product is heat-treated

faster and the desired temperature in the center of the product is reached faster if they are heat-treated at a constant temperature during heat treatment, than when the temperature is increased gradually by a certain value. Recently, in industrial conditions, the method of dry heat treatment by means of microwaves has become widespread. Meat processed by microwave cooking requires much less time to reach the final temperature of the heat treatment. Due to heat transfer by radiation, the product is much more uniform across the cross-section without the pronounced characteristic brownish color, which appears in meat samples processed by the convective method of heat transfer in convection ovens as described in the literature (Gagić, 2016). Before the heat treatment, the meat is reddish in color, and after the heat treatment, depending on the heat treatment mode, it turns light during the heat treatment by cooking to dark brown during the heat treatment by baking and frying. As a result of these changes, there are color changes during the heat treatment in the spectrum from light red to brown depending on the heat treatment mode, the speed of the treatment and the height of the temperature during the heat treatment. Almost all proteins are denatured during the heat treatment of meat, which results in dramatic changes in the color of the meat. Myoglobin denatures at somewhere around 60°C. The change in meat color during heat treatment depends on the degree of denaturation of the three forms of myoglobin. The texture of the meat is closely related to the age, species, sex, race and nutrition of the animal, i.e. the factors that determine the structure of the muscle tissue, the development and properties of the connective tissue and the amount of intramuscular fatty tissue, as well as their connection in the meat. The texture of the meat depends on the intensity of the postmortem changes, the skeletal structure immediately after slaughtering the animal is soft-elastic, and a few hours after that it loses its elasticity and becomes firmer, which is a consequence, first of all, of the development of postmortem rigor. The stronger the muscle contraction, the firmer the meat becomes. The meat acquires a firmer consistency during cooling due to hardening of intermuscular and intramuscular fat. Meat softens only during ripening, as a result of structural changes in myofibrils, collagen, etc. It is known that the ability of meat to bind water, whether it is related to the appearance of postmortem rigor or the speed of postmortem glycolysis, significantly affects the structure and texture of meat (Vuković, 2006). An increase in the proportion of thermostable collagen cross-links in older animals has a significant effect on meat tenderness. The tenderness of the meat increases slightly with increasing heat treatment temperature up to between 60°C and 70°C, when it begins to stagnate or fall slightly. The hardness of meat changes significantly with an increase in temperature during heat treatment, as well as with a change in the heat treatment mode. As a rule, all products treated with dry heat treatment have a higher

hardness for the same temperature value of the product than treated with wet heat treatment. According to (Bouton and Harris, 1981), changes in the behavior of rheological properties with increasing temperature are directly related to changes in proteins (myofibrillar and connective tissue proteins). Heating leads to softening of the connective tissue caused by collagen gelation and an increase in the toughness of muscle fibers caused by thermal coagulation of myofibrillar proteins. In the temperature range from 50 °C to 60 °C, the maximum force for the observed texture property can increase up to 150 %. By increasing the temperature from 60°C to 80°C, the maximum force can remain constant or decrease with increasing temperature by up to 14%. According to (AMSA, 1995), the best sensory properties have samples treated with heat treatment in the temperature range from 61°C to 81°C, which is the interval in which the most intense heat-induced changes in proteins and myofibril decomposition occur. Below this interval, the samples are almost undercooked - cooked with an unsatisfactory aroma and excessive toughness. Above this temperature interval, the samples are too dry and hard, which is especially pronounced during heat treatment by baking. Also, above this interval, in samples processed by heat treatment by baking, a large burn of the surface of the samples appears, especially at 100°C. The heat treatment of the meat is completed by reaching a temperature in the center of the sample of at least 71°C. In this way, the sample is considered to be microbiologically correct after heat treatment by the American Meat Science Association (Baltić and Karabasil, 2011).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analyzing the results of the questionnaire on knowledge of the basic principles of heat processing of food in a modern way, the following indicators were obtained according to the graphic representation:

Age and gender characteristics of the respondents

Out of a total of 52 respondents, 9 respondents are female while 43 respondents are male (graph 1). The situation is similar in other countries of the world.¹³

¹³ Od 3300 šefova iz 28 zemalja uvrštenih u prestižni Michelinov vodič, tek 169 žena nagrađeno je čuvenim zvjezdicama što je manje od šest posto. Za isti posao slabije su plaćene od kolega, sporije napreduju, a uspon obično završi kada zasnuju porodicu.

The age of the respondents is that they are between the ages of 24 and 66, and according to the following shares: From 24 to 34 there are 13 respondents, from 34 to 44 there are 31 respondents, while there are 8 of them over 44 years of age.

Work experience

The work experience of the respondents is shown in the following graph, from which it can be seen that 8 respondents have less than 10 years of experience, while 26 of them have from 10 to 20 years of experience. The remaining 18 respondents have more than 20 years of experience.

Graph 3, RESPONDENT'S WORK EXPERIENCE

Educational structure

Analyzing the respondents' education, the largest percentage of respondents completed secondary school, 21, followed by 15 of them higher education, while 16 respondents have a university degree. Of the 16 respondents who answered that they had a university education, 4 of them obtained a master's or master's degree, while 12 of them completed their education in the first cycle of studies.

Graph 4, DEGREE OF EDUCATION

Basic education in methods and technology of food preparation there are 17 of them, while 35 interviewees started their careers as people who did not have formal education in the mentioned field and continued to improve. It is interesting that all respondents stated that they regularly attend seminars and educations that include methods and technology of food preparation, as well as participation in competitions of professional associations of which they are members.

Graph 5, FORMAL EDUCATION IN THE FIELD OF FOOD PREPARATION

As many as 39 respondents stated that they had training on food safety, while 13 of them did not have the specified training, which is certainly a large number considering the category of facilities that were chosen for the research.

Graph 6, FOOD SAFETY TRAINING

Certification and degree of risk

Out of 52 respondents, 43 respondents answered affirmatively whether the catering establishments where they work are certified by the credit rating agency for quality food handling and the way they are prepared. Therefore, it is concluded that 9 respondents work in establishments that do not have the specified type of certificate, which brings those establishments into the category of medium-risk establishments when it comes to food safety.

Graph 7, CERTIFICATION OF FACILITIES FOR FOOD PREPARATION

When talking about the knowledge of risks in the food preparation process, the majority of respondents declared that they did not know the degree of risk to which their facility is exposed when it comes to food preparation technology and applied standards. Specifically, 48 of them do not know in which risk category they fall, while three respondents answered that they do not see a risk in the way they work, and that their safety concerns belong to low-risk facilities. This is especially important when it comes to establishments that also have confectionery departments. Out of the mentioned facilities, 32 of them independently prepare cakes and cookies.

Graph 8, BELONGING TO A RISK GROUP, KNOWLEDGE OF MEMBERSHIP

CONCLUSION

Through the stated theoretical-practical norms as well as the results of the survey in this paper, the conclusion is clearly drawn that human resources in the culinary and tourism industry in general must know modern technologies and ways of managing foodstuffs, as well as their thermal processing in the process of food preparation. Culinary art first of all stems from human needs but possibilities, which clearly warns that the possibilities are often far below the real needs, as well as the set standards. Knowledge of the safety aspects of food processing is a generally accepted norm and as such has experienced strong progress and has become imperative in the operation of catering facilities. A change in lifestyle, as well as material possibilities, has led to a change in lifestyle habits. There is no doubt that today we live in a time that is oriented towards the consumption of a large amount of meat, which is very often accompanied by a reduced dose of security narrative, which increases the risk of business. The people who manage and make decisions in catering facilities in the observation area are younger people whose experience is roughly in the middle of their career, and among whom at the same time the middle level of vocational training dominates.

The results of the survey show that the percentage of people who do not have formal education in the respective field is the percentage in which they should realistically have it. Nevertheless, with a well-crafted human resources development policy, it is possible to significantly improve the above-mentioned problem. In the professional industrial culinary world this is already an imperative that will continue to stretch into the decades ahead. It is likely that the growth trend in the catering market will be recorded by restaurants that accept this fact. In this sense, the responsibility of the leaders in gastronomy lies in the fact that they accept the necessary changes and remove the recorded shortcomings that the questionnaire indicates. The establishment and realization of trends in a certain technology comes first of all from the legal regulator and as such is an imperative imposed on the tourism industry. It can be concluded that the presented results provide a sufficient framework for the beginning of a serious discussion about the state of the observed problem, but at the same time show room for improvement of the overall state. What is of real concern is the degree of risk that is present and not known as such, and it is necessary to work on activities that reduce or completely eliminate the presence of risk in the way food is prepared by certifying the way of work with various safety certificates. It is important to continuously conduct staff training and establish and simplify procedures when it comes to the degree of safety and risk elimination. It is important to mention that it is a very positive fact that

all the respondents showed their willingness to participate in the survey, which is not always the case, and that they showed their willingness to familiarize themselves with the results and to use them in the further improvement of their work, which is an important social goal of any research.

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